

ДОРИ-ДАРМОНЛАР ТАРИХИ ВА УЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИ ЎРГАНИШНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ

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Аннотация. Ушбу маърузада фармацевтикада қўлланилаётган айрим дори дармонларнинг ишлаб чиқарилиш тарихи ва уларнинг инсонлар соғлиғини сақлаш ва тиклашдаги аҳамияти дидактик, тиббий ҳамда физиологик жиҳатдан ёритиб берилган.

Калим сўзлар: фармацевтика, фармокопея, дори-дармон, тиббиёт, физиология, алкалоид.

Abstract. In this report, the history of the production of some drugs used in pharmaceuticals and their significance in maintaining and restoring human health are highlighted in didactic, medical and physiological terms.

Keywords: pharmaceuticals, pharmacopeia, medicine, medicine, physiology, alkaloid.

Maintaining and restoring human health has been an urgent problem at all stages of society's development. The connection between the standard of living and the way of life of mankind with various aspects of education and upbringing is covered in detail in many scientific and scientific-methodical literatures [1-10].

Preservation and restoration of human health has been an urgent problem at all stages of the development of society. In addition to the extraction of natural medicines from plant and animal materials available in nature, in parallel, the creation of drugs by the synthesis method and their use in medicine have been carried out.

Today, based on the achievements of chemistry, more than 500 new substances are being synthesized in the world every day. It is known in medicine that some of them are used for the treatment of various diseases.

But 150 years ago, only one drug was put into production per year. New drugs should be preferred to replace old ones. But several "old" drugs are still living in the pharmacopoeia. One of these is nitroglycerin. Italian chemist A. It was synthesized by Sobrero and introduced to medicine by English doctors Branton and Richardson in 1860. Nitroglycerin has taken an important place in the treatment of angina pectoris. Along with nitroglycerin, amyl nitrate, offered by Branton, expands the blood vessels of the skin at a faster rate, easing the work of the heart. Erinite, nitrosorbites are also used for these purposes.

It is known that an increase in cholesterol in the body causes rapid aging of a person. Synthesized beta-sitosterol prevents the absorption of dietary cholesterol into the blood and forces it out of the body.

Currently, most of the drugs are obtained by synthesis. Because the drugs created by nature, which are not found in the flora and fauna, are synthesized chemically.

At the same time, processing natural raw materials and extracting medicines is a separate direction in pharmaceuticals. Several examples can be given.

Alkaloids (derived from the word alkaline) are of great importance in the development of the pharmaceutical industry. The first alkaloid obtained in 1817 was morphine (named after Morpheus, the god of sleep; a euphoric drug derived from the milk of the poppy, also known as the "black drug"). Alkaloids such as morphine, narcotine, codeine, nartheine, thebaine, papaverine

found in opium are used to reduce insomnia and pain, treat cough and other diseases. For the same purposes, preparations such as veronal, sulfonal, and luminal can be used.

Nicotine found in tobacco is a poisonous alkaloid. It affects a person's nerves, causes an increase in blood pressure. It is because of this that blood pressure increases in almost all people who smoke cigarettes for many years. Nicotine gradually covers the chest and causes a cough.

Nicotine can paralyze a person when consumed in large quantities.

In addition to nicotine, tobacco also contains pyrrolidine, nicotelline, nornicotine, nicotirine, anabazin and other alkaloids.

Synthetic nicotine is used as an insecticide in the fight against agricultural pests.

An alkaloid called piperine obtained from garmdori is also used in the preparation of medicines.

An alcohol called reserpine is of great importance in the treatment of blood pressure and mental disorders.

Atropine is obtained by synthesis and has the property of expanding the pupil of the eye. It is used in ophthalmology. Atropine is also used to stop the secretion of saliva, sweat, water and other diseases.

Medicines such as aspirin, pyridone, analgin, phenacytin are used to reduce body temperature and reduce pain and stop headaches.

A drug called quinine obtained from the cinchona tree is used against malaria. Quinine is also obtained synthetically. Acrixin is relatively cheap and can be easily used in place of quinine.

Narcotics that induce deep sleep in the body have also been synthesized. Chloroform, ethyl ether and others are among them. It is known that these drugs are used during heavy operations.

Pilocarpine is an important drug in the treatment of eye pain. The former Soviet scientist N. A. Synthesized by Preobrazhensky. Industrial preparations such as dicholine, butadione, salicylamide have given expected results in the treatment of hypertension, nervous, intestinal, kidney, hip, tuberculosis, headache and other diseases.

In recent years, natural compounds called aitiobiotics have attracted the attention of scientists. Antibiotics play an important role in medicines. They are used not only in medicine, but also in agriculture, food industry and other fields.

Penicillin, aspencillin, aspergillin, which are the main representatives of antibiotics, are used in the treatment of blood and intestinal diseases, and streptomycin is used in the treatment of tuberculosis.

Subtilin, erythrin, thyrothricin, auromycin, chloramphenicol and sarcomycin are also used in the treatment of many diseases. Among the most common drugs, sulfanilamide-type streptocide, sulgin, sulfidin, sulfazol, norsulfazol, sulfadimezin, etc. are important drugs in the treatment of colds, sore throat, dysentery, ulcers, and intestinal diseases.

Alkaloid chemistry in our country was founded by Sabir Yunusovich Yunusov, academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Hero of Labor, and now his students are developing this field in every way.

Currently, the plant raw materials resources of Uzbekistan have been studied at the Institute of Plant Substances Chemistry, and it has been proven that alkaloids are present in many of their species.

Collecting information about the history of the creation and use of drugs, processing them didactically, and conducting research on the formation of the level of rational use of medical drugs

in the population is of great importance in the prevention of medicine.

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